

Lupa-20(29)-ene-3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranoside
from the Roots of *Cordia obliqua*

S. K. SRIVASTAVA, S. D. SRIVASTAVA
 and

S. S. NIGAM

Department of Chemistry, University of Saugar,
 Sagar-470 003

Manuscript received 17 April 1979, revised 15 May 1982,
 accepted 12 November 1982

Cordia obliqua (N. O. Boraginaceae) is a medicinal plant^{1,2} employed in Indian indigenous system of medicine. Very little work on the seeds³ and roots⁴⁻⁶ of this plant has been reported. We report here the isolation of a new triterpene glycoside, lupa-20(29)-ene-3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranoside (I) from the roots of *C. obliqua*.

Experimental and Results

The air dried powdered roots of *Cordia obliqua*, procured from the United Chemicals and Allied Products, Calcutta, were exhaustively extracted with EtOH under reflux. The EtOH extract was filtered, concentrated to 100 ml and poured into excess of water (400 ml) with continuous stirring. The water insoluble material was filtered and extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°). The petroleum ether soluble fraction yielded the reported saponin which was crystallized as a pure compound from CHCl₃-MeOH mixture. It was homogeneous on tlc plates (R_f 0.34 in CHCl₃-MeOH, 9 : 1 v/v and 0.48 in CHCl₃-C₆H₆, 3 : 7 v/v), m.p. 172-73°, C₃₈H₆₀O₅ (M⁺572). (Found : C, 75.54; H, 10.49. C₃₈H₆₀O₅ requires C, 75.52; H, 10.48%). 500 mg of the glycoside was hydrolysed with 50 ml of 7% EtOH-H₂SO₄ for 5 hr at 100°. The hydrolysed product was poured into excess of water. On cooling, a solid (genin) precipitate was obtained which was washed with water and crystallized as white silky needles from hot EtOH, m.p. 212-13°, C₃₀H₅₀O (M⁺426). Found : C, 84.70; H, 11.72. C₃₀H₅₀O requires C, 84.70; H, 11.73%). After the separation of the genin, the aqueous hydrolysate was neutralized with BaCO₃ and was found to contain only L-rhamnose (co-*pc*, co-*tlc* and rhamnosazones m.p. 190-91°). The genin gave all the characteristic tests for triterpenoids⁷. It formed a monoacetate (Ac₂O/py), m.p. 213-14°, C₃₂H₅₂O₂ (M⁺ 468), (Found : C, 82.00; H, 11.10. C₃₂H₅₂O₂ requires C, 82.05; H, 11.11%) and a monobenzoate, m.p. 255-56°, C₃₇H₅₄O₂ (M⁺ 530) (Found : C, 83.75; H, 10.20. C₃₇H₅₄O₂ requires C, 83.77; H, 10.18%) showing the presence of one hydroxyl function in the molecule [ir 3325 cm⁻¹ (OH)]. From the detailed study of the MS [m/e at 426 (M⁺); 411 (M⁺-Me); 408 (M⁺-H₂O); 393 {M⁺-(Me+H₂O)}; 383 (M⁺-C₆H₇); 218, 207, 191, 189 and 187]; ir (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3325 (br, OH), 2941 (Me), 1639 (unsaturation), 1449, 1380, 1300, 1190, 1110, 1042, 1015, 948, 885

and 725 and ¹H nmr (CDCl₃, δ ; TMS, 60 MHz): 0.76, 0.80, 0.86, 0.94, 1.04 and 1.18 (s, 6 $\times$ tert Me), 1.70 (s 3H in CH₃-C=CH₂-) and 4.60-4.70 (d, 2H, vinylic protons), the genin was shown to be lupeol⁸⁻¹⁰ which was confirmed by comparison of m.p., m.m.p. and co-*tlc* with an authentic sample. Periodate oxidation¹¹ consumed 2 moles of periodate with the liberation of 1 mole of HCO₂H per 1 mole of the saponin indicating the presence of only one unit of L-rhamnose in pyranose form. Failure of hydrolysis of the saponin with almond emulsin proved the α -linkage between lupeol and L-rhamnose. The calculation of molecular rotation by Klyne's method¹² [(M)_D for glycoside +270°; (M)_D for lupeol +120°; differences +150° and (M)_D for methyl- α -L-rhamnopyranoside +146°] confirmed the α -linkage in the saponin.

On the basis of this study structure (I) has been assigned to the saponin.

References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C. S. I. R., New Delhi, 1956, 77.
2. K. R. KIRTIKAR and B. D. BASU, "Indian Medicinal Plants", Lalit Mohan Basu Pub., Allahabad, 1955, Vol. 3, p. 1675.
3. R. D. TIWARI, K. C. SRIVASTAVA, S. SHUKLA and R. K. BAJPAI, *Planta Medica*, 1967, 15, 240.
4. J. S. CHAUHAN and S. K. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15, 760.
5. S. K. SRIVASTAVA, M. SULTAN and J. S. CHAUHAN, *Vijnana Parishad Anusandhan Patrika*, 1977, 20, 153.
6. J. S. CHAUHAN, S. K. SRIVASTAVA and M. SULTAN, *Phytochem.*, 1978, 17, 334.
7. M. STEINER and H. HOLTZEM, "Modern Method of Plant Analysis", (Eds.), K. PEACH and M. V. TRACEY, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1955, Vol. 3, p. 64.
8. J. S. CHAUHAN and S. K. SRIVASTAVA, *Phytochem.*, 1978, 17, 1005.
9. A. R. H. COLE and D. G. THORNTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1932.
10. D. H. R. BARTON and P. D. MAYO, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 887.
11. E. L. HIRST and J. K. N. JONES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1659.
12. W. KLYNE, *Biochem. J.*, 1950, 47, xli.